

Strengths and dangers of self and peer assessment in engineering learning. Teachers' and students' perspective

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Abstract

Given the need to use competency assessment systems, a complex problem arises, especially when applying a metric to transversal competencies is intended. In this context, it is possible to use, among other tools, self and peer assessment, so that the first-person perspective of the students is considered among the criteria to quantify aspects that are difficult to measure. Even though it may seem interesting, this strategy is not riskless, at least this is deduced when talking about this topic with some colleagues. It is intended to address a reflection on the advantages of self and peer assessment within engineering assessment, but also analysing the risks involved (lack of maturity, assigning too high grades...). This feeling of risky activity is presented as especially dangerous when it has to be used by teachers who are reluctant to its use. Analysis of collected assessment data and questionnaires addressed to both teachers and students will provide an insight to their opinion about these assessment methods.

Keywords: Assessment in active learning; Self and peer assessment in engineering; Competencies assessment.

1 Introduction

A recent study by Halls et al. (2021) suggests that, after a systematic literature review, a greater focus is required in student engagement in the assessment in engineering education. Involving students in the assessment process may provide interesting outcomes. If students are aware of the relevance of their role in the evaluation process, this process can become a true learning opportunity. Even at a professional level, well supported formative feedback would be required to successfully change workplace culture (Willey & Gardner, 2007). This change is initiated by facilitating individual self-reflection and ongoing improvement while encouraging teams to resolve team issues independently. Maybe the most obvious ways to generate this involvement are self and peer assessment.

As stated in (Boud & Falchikov, 1989) self-assessment refers to the involvement of learners in making judgements about their own learning, particularly about their achievements and the outcomes of their learning and is mostly used for formative assessment to foster reflection on one's own learning processes and results (Dochy et al., 1999). Falchikov (1995) defines peer assessment as the process through which groups of individuals rate their peers. This exercise may or may not entail previous discussion or agreement over criteria. It may involve the use of rating instruments or checklists which have been designed by others before the peer assessment exercise or designed by the user group to meet its particular needs (Dochy et al., 1999).

Besides, both students and teachers find risks in the use of self and peer assessment. Some of the potential risks, that are listed in (Tennant & Crawford, 2019), include the reaction of colleagues and external examiners, demands of time, its robustness, and reliability. Students themselves tends to feel confident in traditional summative assessment methods as unequivocally valid assessment mechanisms (Fernandes et al., 2012), considering summative assessment is in the centre of their concerns and as one of the most important results of their learning process.

There are, notwithstanding, studies that conclude that this active role of students in the assessment process is reliable and fair and contributes to a growth in competence (Dochy et al., 1999), even for first year engineering students (Van Hattum-Janssen & Lourenço, 2008).

Summarizing, some of the commonly cited benefits and risks of self and peer assessment for teachers and students are listed in table 1.

Table 1. Benefits and risks of self and peer assessment (literature review).

Implication	Teacher	Student
Benefits	Improves professional practice in relationship with assessment	Improves learning
	Increases opportunities to monitor student progress and identify potential problems	Supports generic skill development
	Strengthens assessment criteria and marking schemes	Enhances motivation and enthusiasm
	Promotes student-centred learning	Increases level of feedback
Risks	Reactions of Colleagues and External Examiners	Belief in teacher-centred assessment
	Time consuming	Time consuming
	Robustness of Assessment	Feeling that traditional summative assessment is more objective
	Reliability	Fears about the impartiality of other students
	Lack of confidence in students' fairness	Relationship with other students if assessment is not favourable

To be honest, when considering that the fact that self and peer assessment can show a lack of objectivity is perceived as a risk for both parts, we are not much worried about this fact. Moreover, some of the members of the network are defendants of subjective assessment as presented in a past work (Romá, 2007).

2 Context

This work is being developed under the framework of a network project of the University of Alicante pursuing improvement of quality and innovation in higher education by means of specific learning experiences. The main goal of this work is to explore the risks and strengths of self and peer assessment from students' and teachers' perspective together with their feelings in front of that strengths and dangers from a local context, as explained in following sections. Besides, some data is going to be summarized from courses that use, among others, self and peer assessment as a part of their evaluation methods.

In sections 2.1 and 2.2 the context in which the study is being conducted is presented.

2.1 Courses

To analyse the results obtained by the use of self and peer assessment, data from five different courses using these types of assessment in different schemes is going to be used. These are courses from Sound and Image in Telecommunication Engineering (SITE) and Biomedical Engineering (BE) degrees in the University of Alicante Polytechnic School.

Table 2. Use of self and peer assessment in the courses under study.

Course	Year	Self	Peer	Short description
Basic Electronics	1 st	5%	N. A.	General opinion about course and self-performance
Biomedical Signal Processing	3 rd	5%	N. A.	General opinion about course and self-performance
Video Engineering	3 rd	35%	13%	Peer assessment of projects and self-assessment of self-performance (with special focus on transversal skills)
Advanced Audio-visual Systems	4 th	N. A.	40%	Peer assessment of research project and literature review)
Audio-visual Production Facilities	4 th	35%	N. A.	General opinion about course and self-performance

Self and peer assessment are used with different objectives and also with different effects in the final marks of each course. Table 2 summarizes how self and peer assessment is used and their weights in the final course marks. The first course in which self and peer assessment was introduced is Video Engineering (in 2008) and the last one Biomedical Signal Processing (in 2016). The weight in which self and peer assessment affects to the final mark varies from 5% to almost 50% depending on the course design.

Shortly, in first year courses self-assessment is used as a final reflection activity with a modest impact in the final mark. This process is done around two questions, what are the benefits of taking this course and which skills have I developed. In 3rd and 4th courses the self-assessment is used goal-based evaluation in with students have to analyse the degree of fulfilment of transversal skills as stated in course goals.

Using peer-assessment in PBL is interesting as it gives provides students a tool to put their own work in context (especially if all the working teams are trying to solve the same, or at least a very similar, problem).

The data will be used to check if there is correlation between student and teacher appreciation of learning outcomes, and to analyse if students tend to over-grade themselves. As students are asked to deliver justified reports to support the proposed marks, interesting information can be obtained from these reports.

2.2 Perspective

The sources of information to gather teachers' and students' perspective in front of self and peer assessment have been some face-to-face informal interviews (with teachers) and questionnaires sent to both students and teachers. The justified reports mentioned in the previous section will also be used with the purpose of gathering information about students' opinion.

The interviews have been used to collect the general feeling of some colleagues (both using and not using self and peer assessment in their courses). As the questions were intentionally not previously prepared, the goal of these meetings was focused on getting subjective information rather than measurable data.

Students' questionnaire has been sent (sharing a google forms link) mainly to students who are actually enrolled in the courses mentioned in Table 1. The questions have also been sent to students from the Master's degree on Education Research. No personal information is stored to ensuring the anonymity of the respondents. At the moment of writing this report, 60 students have fulfilled the form. Although there is no way to know if the answers come from undergraduate or master's degree students, this is not a key data in the study as we were not looking for correlation between answers and students' affiliation. The first intention was to submit the question only to engineering students, but we finally decided to also include students from the Education Research program. The questionnaire is composed of 23 multiple choice questions (6 about assessment in general, 9 about self-assessment and 8 about peer assessment), and one open answer question.

A similar form has been sent to teachers from the Polytechnic School and the Faculty of Education, with the following structure: 7 multiple choice questions about assessment in general, 5 about self-assessment, 4 about students' position in front of self-assessment, 5 about peer assessment, 5 about students' position in front of

peer assessment, 2 about final thoughts and one open answer question. Unfortunately, although not surprisingly, only 10 people have responded to the form at this moment.

3 Teachers' perspective

With only 10 people answering the questionnaire, there is, obviously, no possibility of getting statistics from the data. Notwithstanding, some insights can be obtained from teachers' opinion that can be correlated with the answers in the informal meetings. To put answers in perspective, almost any of them had made research or training on self or peer assessment and its effect on learning outcomes.

One of the most cited risks (and reasons supporting the decision of not using self and peer assessment) is its lack of reliability or, in other words, not being objective. In fact, only 20% of answers show tendency for subjective assessment, while the 80% rely on the idea of having an objective assessment method. Surprisingly, 30% of the teachers are not able to say if the assessment methods they are using are summative or formative ones. There is a higher than desirable number of teachers who is still evaluating in the same way they were evaluated without considering other options. As can be seen in Figure 1 most of them have never used self or peer assessment in their courses, so some of the opinions expressed may not being supported by experience.

Figure 1. Use of self and peer assessment.

In general, teachers tend to think that students will over-rate themselves when using self-assessment (80%). However, most of teachers think that students are mature enough to carry on with this process (90%). When considering peer assessment there is a slightly lower level of over-rating sensation (70%), while 100% consider that students are able to evaluate their peers in a mature and thoughtful way.

Asking teachers about under what circumstances they will choose self and/or peer assessment in their courses, some interesting answers are listed:

- Reduced number of students and over third year.
- Course content not being too technical (more descriptive).
- I would have to feel that these strategies help student development.
- I would use them if I was responsible of the course or having the support of course responsible.
- Not having to worry about others' opinion.

Our general perception is that teachers who are reluctant to the use of self and peer assessment show a tendency to think that students will not evaluate themselves fairly, even though they consider students to be mature enough to take the assessment responsibility. At the same time these teachers are not aware of the learning outcomes that self and peer assessment can provide.

4 Students' perspective

In this section some of the students' answers to the questionnaire are going to be highlighted. To state a starting point, the answers about the preferred assessment model is presented in figure 2.

Which assessment model do you feel more comfortable with?

Figure 2. Preferred assessment model for students.

It is remarkable that near 50% of students don't know the difference between assessment models. If we want them to be engaged in the learning process and confident in the way they are evaluated, maybe an effort must be done in letting them know about the assessment strategies.

When students are asked if self or peer assessment must have a considerable weight in the final mark, similar results are found when comparing self and peer assessment (Figure 3). It will be interesting to figure out why over 20% of students fully disagree with the use of self or peer assessment as part of the final mark.

Self or peer assessment must have considerable weight of the final mark

Figure 3. Students' opinion about using self and peer assessment with a considerable weight in the final mark.

Most of the students are aware that proposing self-assessment implicitly shows a high level of confidence in themselves, as can be seen in figure 4.

I am aware that by proposing self-assessment a high level of confidence in myself is shown.

Figure 4. Students' awareness of the confident needed to propose self-assessment.

When considering one of the fears expressed by teachers in relation with the tendency of students to over-rate themselves, students' opinion is not the same (figure 5).

Figure 5. Students' awareness of the confident needed to propose self-assessment.

Asking students about under what circumstances they think self and/or peer assessment should be used, some interesting answers are listed:

- There must be a proper rubric to be used as an assessment guide.
- If self-assessment is used, everyone would be more engaged and active in classroom sessions.
- It will be interesting if the teacher reviews the marks of self and peer assessment.
- Inter-personal relationships can be an issue in peer assessment. The classroom mood must be good and relaxed.
- In self-evaluation we can be aware, and learn, from our own mistakes. In peer assessment we can learn from the work done by other students.
- It would be good for students with a well-measured self-criticism. The problem can arise in students who undervalue themselves, and vice versa, students who are more narcissistic who feel they deserve a higher grade than they should be.

Summarizing, students consider themselves as 'fair players' concerning self and peer assessment. With little instruction, they are fully aware about the learning possibilities of this kind of assessment strategy. To ensure they will be confident in this assessment, special care must be taken to ensure personal relationships are not being considered in the assessment. When asking them for their opinion about self and peer assessment, the answers that have been obtained tend to be more mature than expected.

5 Analysis of assessment data

In this section we are going to analyse if students' and teachers' opinion about self and peer assessment are correlated with the data obtained from courses using these types of assessment. Of all the courses presented in Section 2.1, a couple of examples is going to be presented together with some general thoughts.

The way in which self-assessment is addressed is different depending on the course. For first year students, it is necessary to be more directive in the way the instructions are provided to the students. In the case of the Basic Electronics (first year) course, the self-assessment is weighted with a 5% in the final mark. Students are asked to prepare a justified report and a proposed mark, based on the learning goals of the course structured in two questions:

- What skills have I developed by taking this course?
- What are the benefits of having taken this course?

The difference between the self-assessment mark and the final mark (0-10 scale) is displayed for about 750 students between 2011-12 and 2020-21 academic years, together with the average of this difference per year is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Numeric difference between self-assessment and final mark of a first year engineering course. Pink bars indicate the average difference per year.

Even this data come from first year students, which are supposed to be less mature, there is clear consistency in the results. There is a quite stable offset of two points between the marks. The person responsible of the course is quite satisfied with the self-assessment reports and marks. His opinion of this two points' difference is a mix between a slight over-rating and an evaluation scheme that can be improved.

Some results of peer assessment can be obtained from the 3rd year Video engineering course. In this course, peer assessment is used as the main tool in the process of evaluation of projects. Figure 7 presents the difference between peer assessments and teacher marks for the 21 working groups in a given year. The data displayed corresponds with the average of all the marks assigned to each one of the working teams related with one of the projects developed.

In this case it is interesting to consider that, contrary to reluctant teachers' opinion, there is not a general tendency to over-rate if the teacher mark is taken as a reference. Not only is there a high degree of correlation but in half of the cases, students are marking their peers with a more severe criterion. Although Figure 7 depicts data from one year, the tendency we have obtained is similar in almost every year. Little exceptions have been found corresponding with years with reduced number of students (and, logically reduced number of working teams).

Figure 7. Comparison between peer assessment and teacher's marks from a 3rd year engineering course.

The last behaviour to explore is the relationship between the self-perception (self-assessment mark) and the marks assigned to the rest of the teams (peer assessment mark). Figure 8 represents the dispersion comparing the difference between self-assessment mark with the average of the received peer assessment marks ($SA-PA_r$) with the difference between assigned peer assessment and the average mark of all the peer assessments (PA_a-PA_{avg}) for the same 21 teams of Figure 7. The data have been normalized in a ± 1 range.

Figure 8. Relationship between self-perception and assigned peer assessment from a 3rd year engineering course.

Figure 8 shows a clear trend. The groups with the highest level of self-demand ($SA - PA_r < 0$) have a tendency to rate the rest of the groups with higher grades ($PA_a - PA_{avg} > 0$). Likewise, groups that rate themselves with higher grades ($SA - PA_r > 0$) tend to be more demanding when rating the rest of the teams ($PA_a - PA_{avg} < 0$). The global reference provided by the implementation of peer assessment generates a consistent marking reference that it used in the self-assessment when both strategies are used simultaneously.

6 Conclusion

Learning outcomes associated to self and peer assessment have been widely stated in bibliography. However, it is easy to find teachers who are reluctant to the use of these assessment methods. Besides, a considerable number of students don't know the difference between formative and summative assessment. Some effort must be done in training on assessment strategies addressed to both teachers and students to help them be confident in 'non-traditional' assessment methods.

According to teachers' perspective, the main risks associated to self and peer assessment are the lack of reliability, not being confident in student criteria and how to justify evaluation results to other colleagues or external examiner.

One of the most cited fears by students is related with the risk of being assessed by peers biased by personal relationships. Apart from this, students are quite receptive to the use of self and peer assessment showing a clear idea (or intuition) about their benefits.

Acceptable levels of correlation between self and teacher's assessment has been supported by the data analysed. A quite consistent behaviour has been observed. Using peer assessment to evaluate projects, with all working groups solving the same project, has delivered high levels of correlation with teachers' opinion. If self-assessment is used in the same framework, the reference of peers' work becomes a solid basement for the self-assessment.

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